

INFLUENCE OF LYMPHOCYTE SUBPOPULATIONS IN THE TUMOR MICROENVIRONMENT ON BREAST CANCER PROGNOSIS

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Purpose: to study the features of the immune microenvironment of the tumor in breast cancer.

Materials and methods. To improve the diagnosis and treatment of breast cancer by studying the microenvironment of the tumor, its influence on the course and prognosis, we analyzed a group of 457 patients with breast cancer who were examined and treated at the INKHA University Hospital (South Korea) (362 patients) and in TCB RSPMCOR of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan (95 patients).

Results. Of the 240 results of positive expression of CD3 in 202 cases, the results of treatment were successful. Among patients with a favorable outcome of the disease, this subpopulation of lymphocytes was found in 68.9% of cases, while in the group with poor treatment results, the positive expression of this marker was only 23.2% of cases. A positive CD4 status in the group of patients with a favorable outcome of the disease was detected in 67.9% of cases, an unfavorable outcome in 26.8% of patients. 81.9% of patients from the group with a favorable outcome had positive CD4, in the group of patients with an unfavorable symptom, this symptom occurred only in 18.1% of cases, which indicates a high predictive role of this factor ($\chi^2=9.13$, $p<0.001$). Of the 192 positive CD68 tests, 64.1% of

cases were found in the group with a poor prognosis of the disease. In the group of patients with a favorable outcome of the disease, this test was negative in 76.5% of cases, in the group with an unfavorable outcome in only 25%.

Conclusion. Thus, positive expression of CD 68 and negative expression of CD3, CD4, CD8 are prognostically unfavorable signs. While the negative expression of CD 68 and the positive expression of CD3, CD4, CD8 are prognostically favorable signs.